

Table 1. Head loss fraction for PVC and clay drainage pipes in add-saline, low-elevation tract.

Hours after set of drainage	h_e/h_{tot}	
	Slotted PVC pipe	Baked clay pipe
1	0.87	0.25
6	0.80	0.27
12	0.83	0.27
24	0.83	0.28
48	0.88	0.35
72	0.94	0.41

with subsurface drains. PVC pipes with slots 5 cm long and 0.1 cm wide, and baked clay pipes with an effective bell mouth diameter of 15 cm and tail diameter of 12.5 cm were tested. Effective areas of water entry were 162 cm²/m. Performance was measured through head loss fraction: the ratio of entrance head loss (h) to total head (h_{tot}).

Head loss fraction for the clay pipe

Table 2. Monthly variation of pH and EC of irrigation water in the acid-saline soils of Kuttanad (pooled over 1983-88).

	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar
pH	5.4	5.6	4.4	5.2	5.2	5.3	5.4	5.2	5.3	5.2	5.4	6.1
EC	2.7	2.5	2.2	1.2	0.8	1.0	1.0	0.9	1.3	1.0	0.8	0.9

drain was low and its performance moderate (Table 1). PVC slotted pipes give very poor performance, possibly because of inadequate slot size and/or clogging of the slots by iron oxides.

We also measured irrigation water quality for five hydrological years, 1983-88. Water samples were collected from all irrigation sources at weekly intervals and analyzed for pH and EC. The optimum 5.0-6.0 pH for rice occurred in all months except Jun; the optimum EC of 0.8-1.4 dS/m occurred Jul-Mar (Table 2).

These favorable soil chemical properties are attained primarily during the southwest monsoon. ■

Farming systems

Integrated nutrient management in rice - mustard cropping sequence

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We studied the effect of green manure (GM) *Sesbania aculeata*, blue-green algae (BGA), paper mill sludge (PMS), and Udaipur rock phosphate (URP) with urea, single superphosphate (SSP), and muriate of potash (MP) on wet season rice and succeeding dry season mustard in 1988-89.

Soil was sandy loam, acidic, pH 5.5, 0.3% organic C, 0.03% total N, CEC 7.15 cmol/kg, 24 kg available P/ha, and 155 kg available K/ha.

S. aculeata was sown the first week of Jun and fertilized at 13.2 and 22.0 kg P/ha through SSP, and URP, respectively (see table). At 45 d after sowing (DAS), fresh biomass weighing about 10 t/ha (0.68% N fresh weight basis) was incorporated. Rice variety Parijat was transplanted at 15- × 15-cm spacing 5 d after GM incorporation.

PMS (75% CaCO₃) at one-half the lime requirement of 4.5 t CaCO₃ was added 7 d before transplanting rice. P and R were applied as basal. N was applied to rice in three splits.

BGA algal crust at 10 kg/ha was inoculated 7 d after transplanting. N added through BGA at 30 d after inoculation was estimated at 10.9 kg/ha.

Mustard cultivar M27 was sown at 30- × 10-cm spacing in residual soil moisture immediately after rice harvest the first week of Nov. P and K were applied as basal and N was applied in two splits.

Treatments were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Yields with application of PMS + 60-13-25 and 40-9-17 kg NPK/ha (with and without S) to rice and mustard, respectively, were the highest and comparable to that with GM + 13 kg P/ha + 20-0-25 and 40-9-17 kg NPK/ha (see table). The GM treatment saved 40 kg fertilizer N/ha in rice.

Direct and residual effect of BGA on grain yield of both crops were not pronounced. This might be due to low N from BGA in the acidic soil environment with intermittent dry-wet conditions.

Highest net return and cost:benefit ratio were with PMS + 60-13-25 and 40-9-17 kg NPK/ha (without S) and GM + 13 kg P/ha + 20-0-25 and 40-9-17 kg NPK/ha. ■

Effect of biochemical and chemical fertilizers and paper mill sludge on grain yield and economics of rice + mustard. Orissa, India.

Treatment ^a (kg NPK/ha)		Grain yield (t/ha)		Gross return (\$/ha)	Total cost (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Benefit: cost ratio
Wet season	Dry season	Rice	Mustard				
60-13-25	40-9-17	2.0	0.7	622.3	355.7	266.6	1.75
60-22 ^b -25	40-0-16	1.9	0.7	626.8	347.0	279.8	1.81
BGA+40-13-25	40-9-17	1.8	0.7	611.1	352.9	258.2	1.73
GM ^c +20-0-25	40-9-17	2.2	0.8	703.8	349.6	354.2	2.01
GM ^c +BFA+0-0-25	40-9-17	1.8	0.8	629.3	347.0	282.3	1.81
GM ^d +20-0-25	40-0-17	2.1	0.8	670.6	340.2	330.4	1.97
PMS+60-13-25	40-9-17	2.3	0.8	714.9	364.5	350.4	1.96
PMS+60-13-25 (-S)	40-9-17 (3) + gypsum	2.2	0.9	768.7	366.5	402.2	2.10
LSD (0.05)		0.2	0.1			50.3	-

^aBGA =blue-green algae. GM = green manuring with *S. aculeata*. Gypsum applied at 250 kg/ha. PMS =paper mill sludge. ^b50% as a single superphosphate and 50% through Udaipur rock phosphate. ^c13 kg P/ha as single superphosphate was applied to *S. aculeata*. ^d22.0 kg P/ha was applied to *S. aculeata* as Udaipur rock phosphate.

ERRATA

New IRRI publications, 16 (2) (Apr 1991), 25. Line 1 should read: *Editing and publication-a training manual*, by I. Montagnes.

C.V. Singh et al. Rice-based intercropping systems by rainfed upland conditions of Chotanagpur plateau. 15 (3) (Jun 1990), 36.

In column 1, the spacings should read "20-, 45-,45-, 45, and 75-cm."

In column 3 of the text and in the last column of the table, "equivalency" should be "equivalent."